

STANJE ŽIVOTNE SREDINE ZNAČAJNIH KARSTNIH IZVORA U BUGARSKOJ

ENVIRONMENTAL STATUS OF SIGNIFICANT KARST SPRINGS IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT: *In connection with the preparation of a Global and National list under the MIKAS Project of the most important karst springs, it is necessary to evaluate and compare them according to several criteria. The aim of the present study is to determine the ecological status of pre-selected more important karst springs in Bulgaria, which will facilitate the application of one of the regulated criteria - the ecological one. This status is determined according to the nature protection legal framework. After a GIS analysis, it was determined in which protected areas the selected springs and their feeding areas are located. According to the legal measures for the protection of the environment and the foreseen restrictions, 5 groups with different significance of the ecological status are separated. It is recommended that some springs with a low or no ecological status be proposed for the acquisition of the status of protected areas or natural landmarks.*

Key words: *karst spring, ecological status, environmental legislation, Project MIKAS, Bulgaria*

INTRODUCTION

The karst springs are important as a source of water for the population, and represent unique natural objects that must be preserved (Maksimovich, 1969, Bögli, 1980, Ford & Williams, 2007, Kresic & Stevanovic, 2010, Stevanovic, 2019, Goldscheider et al., 2020, De Waele & Gutiérrez, 2022). In order to characterize and popularize the most interesting of them in the world, the International Association of Hydrogeologists (IAH) started a large international project Most Important Karst Aquifer Karst Springs (MIKAS) (Stevanovic, 2023). Bulgaria also participated in the implementation of this project (Benderev, 2022, Benderev et al., 2023). The choice of which of the many springs in different countries to be included in the Global and National lists is based on 5 criteria: historical, aesthetic, economic, scientific and ecological. The purpose of the present study is to assess the ecological status of pre-selected more important springs in Bulgaria, as an important factor for their ecological assessment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The general principles for choosing the most important springs for each country and for the world are regulated in a methodology previously developed by the Advisory Board of the MIKAS project (Stevanovic, 2023). Given that there is a significant number of karst springs in Bulgaria (over 200), with different conditions of formation, quantitative and qualitative characteristics (Boyadzhiev, 1964, Antonov & Danchev, 1980, Damyanova, 2021, 2022) it was necessary to pre-selection was held. The pre-selection was done by Benderev et al. (2023), and 42 springs with a relatively higher average (over 200 L/s) or maximum (over 1000 L/s) flow rate were selected for preliminary evaluation, as well as some springs with a lower flow rate, but having important economic, scientific or other importance (Figure 1). For each spring, a quantitative assessment was carried out according to the accepted criteria under the MIKAS Project. One of the important factors that needs to be included in the assessment is the ecological status of the respective spring, which is determined by the environmental protection legal framework of the respective country. Along with the specific place of occurrence of the karst waters on the surface, it is important to assess the ecological status of their catchment areas in which their recharge takes place.

Figure 1. Karst springs and outcrops of karst rocks in Bulgaria. Legend: 1. outcrops of karstified rocks 2. karst springs 3. selected karst springs

Nature protection in Bulgaria has a long history. The first Silkosia Reserve in Strandzha Mountain was declared by a decision of the Council of Ministers in 1931, and the first Vitosha Nature Park was declared in 1934. The first official normative document for the environment protection was adopted in 1936. - Ordinance-law for the protection of native nature, signed by Tsar Boris III (Boev, 2008). Currently, the Protected Territories Act (1998) is applied to assess the ecological status of the selected springs. According to it and the corresponding sub-normative documents in our country, 1048 protected areas are regulated:

- Reserves (R)- 55
- Maintained reserves (MR) - 35
- National parks (NtP) - 3
- Nature parks (NrP, - 11
- Protected areas (PA) – 590
- Natural landmarks(NL)- 354

An initial review of these protected areas was made and it was determined, using GIS, which of them refer to specific karst springs. Additionally, it was determined whether any of the pre-selected springs or their catchment falls within the territory of other protected areas. Given that some of the springs are directly connected to a specific cave, data provided by Jalov (2006) were also used. It was established which of the specified springs and their catchments fall into the NATURA 2000 areas for biodiversity habitats (N-Bio) and for birds (N-Brd) (occupying about 35% of the country's territory), which due to being aimed at living nature have an indirect relation to the ecological status of karst springs.

RESULTS

According to the Law on Protected Areas, territories with samples of natural ecosystems and habitats are declared reserves. They are characterized by the highest degree of restrictions. The main attention is directed to the protection of plant and animal species, and not to inanimate nature, including karst springs. Therefore, these springs are not the object of direct conservation interest, but due to the serious measures, people's access to them is limited and they have a high degree of protection. Of the pre-selected significant springs and/or parts of their recharge areas, falling within the scope of the reserves are #10 Bistrets and #22 Pavolche near the town of Vratsa, #13 Kumanitsa and #18 Tazha in the Central Balkan.

In contrast to reserves, maintenance, guidance, regulation or restoration measures are allowed in maintained reserves. Some of the protected reserves in Bulgaria include karst basins with their springs, but none of the selected springs fall within their territory.

Territories, whose borders do not include settlements and which include natural ecosystems with a wide variety of plant and animal species and habitats, with characteristic and remarkable landscapes and objects of inanimate nature, are declared National Parks. In Bulgaria, 3 National Parks have been established - Pirin, Central Balkan and Rila, and in the first two the karst is widespread. In 1983, Pirin National Park has been included in the list of the World Heritage Convention of UNESCO, with an area of 27 000 ha. Of the selected more significant springs, two (No. 13 Kumanitsa and No. 18 Tazha.) are within the frames of the Central Balkan National Park, and the entire catchment area of the karst springs Yazo and Kyoshka near Razlog (No. 16 a, b) are on the territory of the Pirin National Park, although the springs themselves are outside it.

In the case of natural parks, in contrast to national parks, it is permissible to have settlements and settlement systems on their territory. In these natural parks, productions and activities can be carried out that do not pollute the environment and are consistent with their management plans. Of the pre-selected significant springs for the country, only one, together with its catchment, is within the boundaries of Vitosha Natural Park - Vreloto (No.32).

The protected areas are declared as: territories with characteristic or remarkable landscapes, including those that are the result of the harmonious coexistence of man and nature; habitats of threatened rare or vulnerable plant and animal species and communities. Some of the selected more important karst springs in Bulgaria have been declared protected areas - No. 2 Glava Panega, No. 6 Hotnitsa, one of the two springs near Razlog (No. 16) - Kyoshka, No. 33 Varovitets. This group of territories also includes some caves from which karst springs flow, such as No. 5 Toplya, No. 7 Musina, No. 9 Krushuna. Some of the protected areas are located in the immediate vicinity of some karst springs, such as the "Skaklya" waterfall, next to which is a spring of the same name at Bov (No. 31), the "Ponorite" karst formations next to the Musina spring (No. 7), "Nastanska mogila" next to spring No. 17 Nastan, the landscape-historical complex "Dryanovo Monastery", which includes spring No. 36 Andaka.

The natural landmarks are characteristic objects of inanimate nature, which are of exceptional value due to their inherent rarity, representativeness, aesthetics, or which are important for science and culture. Five of the selected springs belong to this category: No. 2 - Glava Panega, No. 4 - Kotel springs, No. 7 - Musina Cave (spring) and, No. 33 - Varovitets and No. 38 - the springs near the village of Bezden, as well as the Temnata Dupka Cave near Lakatnik connected to spring No 3 Zhitolyub.

With relatively fewer restrictions on anthropogenic activities are the protected areas belonging to the ecological network Natura 2000, which are regulated in accordance with two main directives for the protection of the environment of the European Union - Directive 92/43/EEC for the protection of natural habitats and wild flora and fauna and Directive 2009/147/EC on the protection of wild birds. They occupy about 35% of the territory of Bulgaria and in most cases do not have a significant importance for increasing the ecological status of karst springs, but help to limit human activity in their catchment areas.

When summarizing the results obtained after applying GIS, it was found that about 36% (15 springs) of the pre-selected significant karst springs have an ecological status regulated by the state, falling into protected areas or natural landmarks (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

The analysis of the obtained results allows the selected karst springs in Bulgaria to be divided into several groups according to their ecological status (Figure 2):

1 - Springs with the highest ecological status are those that fall, together with their catchment areas, within the boundaries of National Parks (5 springs). The limits of potential impact regulated by the law and the mandatory guarding and protection of their territories guarantee the protection not only of the places of occurrence of the karst springs on the surface, but also their quantities and qualities, which are formed in the recharge areas. The two springs at Razlog (which are considered together) can also be referred to this group, given that their areas for the formation of their outflow almost entirely fall within the territories of Pirin National Park, but the springs themselves are outside it. The reason for this is that one of the springs - "Kyoshka" (No. 16a) has been declared a natural landmark, and the other - "Yazo" (No. 16b) is in the first zone of its Sanitary protection zone;

2 - Springs with a high ecological status (11 springs) include those that have been declared protected areas or natural landmarks, and their catchment areas are within Natura 2000 zones. This guarantees the protection of the springs themselves and limited areas around them. On the other hand,

although human activity is allowed in NATURA 2000 areas, there are still regulated restrictions and prohibitions. This group also includes spring No. 32 "Vreloto", which, together with its recharge area, falls within the scope of the "Vitosha" Nature Park;

3- With a medium ecological status are those springs (3 springs), which are declared protected areas or natural landmarks, but their recharge areas are without ecological protection;

4 – Low ecological status (12 springs) - springs with their catchment areas (or only their catchment areas) that fall into NATURA 2000 zones. In these areas, human activities that would mainly have an impact on biodiversity and not on non-living nature and waters are restricted;

5 – Springs without an established ecological status (11 springs) – these are springs that do not fall into regulated protected areas. Of course, this does not include the springs that are used for drinking water supply and for which sanitary protection zones have been established.

Table 1. Pre-selected karst springs and their belonging to protected areas (protected areas are given in gray color, with R is noted that the corresponding spring does not fall within the scope of the protected area, but the part of its catchment area)

	Selected springs	R	MR	NtP	NrP	PA	NL	N-Bio	N-Brd
1	Iskrets							R	
2	Glava Panega								
3	Lakatnik							R	
4	Kotel								
5	Toplya							R	
6	Hotnitza								
7	Musina								
8	Trigrad								
9	Krushuna							R	R
10	Bistrets, Vratza								
11	Devnya								
12	Beden								
13	Kumanica	R							
14	Pali Lula							R	
15	Beli Izvor								
16a	Razlog (Kyoshka)			R					
16b	Razlog (Yazo)	R		R					
17	Nastan								
18	Tazha	R							
19	Hubcha								
20	Tri Voditsi					R		R	
21	Kobilyak							R	
22	Pavolche								
23	Kleptuza								R
24	Kameno Pole							R	
25	Krachimir								
26	Zli dol							R	
27	Gabare								
28	Krapetz								
29	Muldava								
30	Montana								
31	Skaklya, Bov								
32	Vreloto							R	
33	Varovitets, Etropole								
34	Musomishta							R	
35	Popovec, Etropole								
36	Andaka, Dryanovo								
37	Brauna - Smolyan								
38	Bistrec - Bezden								R
39	Dolni Rakovetz								
40	Tserovo								
41	Transka Bankya							R	
42	Belovo								

Figure 2. Distribution by ecological status of the previously selected karst springs

It is established that more than half of the pre-selected karst springs in Bulgaria have a low or no regulated ecological status. This necessitates that some of the more important and interesting of them be proposed to receive the status of protected areas or natural landmarks. Of course, such springs that are located in a completely urban environment (No. 37 "Brauna" in the city of Smolyan, No. 35 "Popovets" in Etropole) or with significant anthropogenic intervention (the spring at the village of Nastan), should be excluded. In our opinion, initial attention to increase the ecological status should be directed to the springs proposed for inclusion in the lists under the MIKAS Project - No. 1 Iskrets and No. 11 Devnya springs, to springs connected with interesting caves and karst sites, such as the spring near Tserovo (No. 40), No. 25 Krachimirsko Vrelo, as well as the subthermal springs at No. 34 Musomishta and No. 41 Transka Bankya.

CONCLUSION

Ecological status is an important part of one of the accepted criteria for determining the importance of karst springs with a view to their inclusion in the Global and National List under the MIKAS Project. A major factor in what measures and restrictions are legally regulated to ensure the preservation of the natural state of the respective sites. In order to be able to compare and evaluate pre-selected more significant karst springs in Bulgaria, they are systematized into 5 groups, according to whether they fall into protected areas and if they do, what is their status, what activities are allowed and what restrictions are mandatory. It was established that more than half of the selected springs have a low or no ecological status, which means that in the future the more interesting ones will be proposed to the Ministry of Environment and Water for their approval as protected sites or natural landmarks.

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